

W5 – Dissemination and exploitation

D5.1-5.3 Webpage, social media, dissemination and exploitation

Abstract

This deliverable of "Webpage, social media, dissemination and exploitation" contains a detailed description of the webpage architecture, which is a window for the general audience and stakeholders, as well as, a server to storage and real-time visualization of all collected data in the field and main outcomes of the project.

In addition, this and successive deliverables of the WP5 summarize all the social media interactions and dissemination activities.

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Project information

Project information	
<i>Project number</i>	101032024
<i>Project acronym</i>	Smart Fishways
<i>Project title</i>	Adapting fishways to hydrological and climatic uncertainty
<i>Starting date</i>	01/09/2021
<i>Duration</i>	2 years
<i>Call identifier</i>	MSCA-IF-2020 - Individual Fellowships
<i>Abstract</i>	<p>Modern society currently requires large volumes of fresh water. The result is the installation of river barriers, causing the fragmentation of habitats as well as changes in the ecology of freshwater systems. Stepped fishways can allow fish to move freely up rivers to complete their life cycle. However, the variability of rivers modifies the hydraulic conditions within fishways, affecting the free movement of fish.</p> <p>Smart Fishways is an EU-funded project, which aims to assess the effect of hydrological variability on stepped fishways and to develop a technological and methodological framework to monitor fishways' performance in real-time. By combining fish biology, hydraulics and sensor networks, a new generation of smart fishways will be created, capable of self-deciding their optimal configuration.</p>
<i>Work Package number</i>	W5 Dissemination and exploitation
<i>Deliverable</i>	D5.1-5.3 Webpage, social media, dissemination and exploitation

Document Control Page

Document control Page	
<i>Title</i>	D5.1-5.3 Webpage, social media, dissemination and exploitation
<i>Creator</i>	Juan Francisco Fuentes-Pérez
<i>Description</i>	<p>This deliverable of "Webpage and Social media" contains a detailed description of the webpage architecture, which is a window for the general audience and stakeholders, as well as, a server to storage and real-time visualization of all collected data in the field and main outcomes of the project.</p> <p>In addition, this and successive deliverables of the WP5 summarize all the social media interactions and dissemination activities.</p>
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1. Introduction

The WP5 takes care of all dissemination and exploitation activities. Deliverables inside this WP summarize the actions performed to reach different audiences.

The following document is the deliverable of WP5, describing the architecture of the developed webpage as well as the interactions with target audiences.

2. Logo and Webpage

During the first month of the project, a logo (Figure 1) and a webpage (with two domains: www.smartfishways.eu and www.smartfishways.com) have been developed.

Figure 1. Explained logo of Smart Fishways project.

The logo was developed by the IP of the project and it tries to collect in a single figure the multidisciplinary nature of the project. This unique logo makes the project easily identifiable and it serves as a signature for any related visual media.

The webpage was also developed by the IP of the project. This task was not subcontracted to have full control of its code, as it is a fundamental part of data management and storage. The webpage is regularly updated and it has two main objectives:

1. Serve as a window for all audiences interested in the project.
2. Serve as an online server for all the publications, deliverables, and collected data in the project.

Figure 2. Home page of Smart Fishways web.

The web has a simple design composed of differentiated pages distributed as follows:

- **Home:** Presentation of the project, main objectives, and list of main partners and collaborators.
- **News:** List and information of actions and dissemination activities performed within the project.
- **Deliverables and Publications:** Collection of documents produced in the project, together with downloading resources.
- **Real-Time:** Page that shows real-time data of study cases, as well as the possibility of downloading for authorized users.
- **Technology:** List of technologies developed within the project.
- **Contact:** Contact information and form, as well as, a short 'about us' section.

Check the [webpage](#) for more information.

Figure 3. Different HTML pages available on the Smart Fishway web.

3. Social media

In addition to the webpage and its news section, dissemination will be performed using social media platforms. Target social media platforms are X (before known as Twitter), Facebook and YouTube.

Concerning Facebook, the Facebook account of the Group of Applied Ecohydraulics will be used, adding specific tags of the project. Link to [Facebook](#).

When it comes to X, a specific account has been opened for the project, all news of the project in a tweet format will be posted together with relevant links. Link to [X](#).

For YouTube, IP's personal YouTube account will be used ([link](#)) to post exclusive videos on small knowledge pills about electronics not shared in other related channels. Additionally, to a lesser extent, the University of Valladolid's (UVA) YouTube channel will also be utilized ([link](#)).

4. Summary of performed activities

Table 1 summarizes the conducted activities until the publication of this deliverable:

Table 1. Summary of dissemination and exploitation activities until 18/12/23.

Date	Description	Audience	Associated links
2024	Publication of the Paper: "Effect of Hydrological Variability on Fishways and Its Implications in Their Management"	Scientific community	Under Review
2024	Publication of the Paper: "Comparative study of natural fibres to improve insulation in wooden beehives using sensor networks"	Scientific community	Under Review
2024	Publication of the Paper: "Suitability of 2D depth-averaged simulations to support predictions of cyprinids passage through Vertical Slot Fishways"	Scientific community	Under Review
2024	Publication of the Paper: "A step forward in fishway engineering: validation and implementation of advanced algorithms for effective stepped fishway design, modeling, and retrofitting"	Scientific community	In press N/A
05.05.2024	Smart Fishways at Fish Passage Conference	Scientific community Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	N/A
05.05.2024	DIY Workshop on Environmental Sensing in Canada: Smart Fishways at the Fish Passage Conference	Scientific community Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	N/A
02.2024	Official Presentation of Escalas in Collaboration with the Duero River Water Authority, Itagra.ct, and the University of Valladolid (UVA)	Public administration and policymakers General audience	N/A
12.12.2023	Session on AI for the technical staff of Technology Centers (AIRInstitute, Itagra.ct, Cartif and Cesefor) focusing on the integration of technology with natural and cultural heritage	Industry-private companies	Twitter

15.11.2023	Open House Day for the Science Week on "Water, Forests, and Monitoring of Rivers and Fish Fauna"	General audience	Twitter
30.10.2023	Field visit and presentation of Smart Fishways, UVA	Scientific community General audience	Twitter
26.10.2023	Open House Day at IUFOR to present Smart Fishway technology	Scientific community General audience	Twitter
19.10.2023	Collaboration between Smart Fishways and the Kantauribai Project: Initial Meeting and the First Installations	Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	Twitter
02.10.2023	Presentation of Fish Tracker: An Infrared-Based Fish Counting Device	General audience	Twitter
21.06.2023	Presentations on Adaptive management and Smart Fishways at Congreso Ibérico de Restauración Fluvial RESTAURARÍOS	Scientific community Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	Abstract Abstract Abstract
22.05.2023	Installation of Smart Fishway Sensor Network in Beehives to Assess the Influence of Climate on Honey Production	General audience	Twitter News
13.04.2023	Publication of the Paper: "Bidirectional connectivity on step-pool fishways: Analyzing the case of small hydropower plants"	Scientific community	Paper
05.04.2023	Meeting and Inspection of Fixed Installations in Northern Portugal	Scientific community Industry-private companies General audience	Twitter Twitter
22.03.2023	Smart Fishways presentation at CERIS, Portugal	Scientific community	N/A
22.02.2023	Publication of the Paper: "Digitalization and real-time control to mitigate environmental impacts of artificial barriers in rivers: Focus on hydropower systems and European priorities"	Scientific community	Paper
08.02.2023	Presentation of Smart Fishway Technology at the 'Intelligent Rural Territory' Meeting in Castilla y León	Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	Twitter News News
13.02.2023	Field Visit to Study Cases in Portugal and Presentation of Smart Fishway Technology	Scientific community Industry-private companies	Twitter
23.01.2023	Smart Fishways in at the XVII Young Forest Researchers Meeting On Conservation And Sustainable Use Of Forest Systems	Scientific community	Twitter
10.01.2023	Publication of the Paper: "Effect of thermovelocity barriers on fish: influence of water temperature, flow velocity and body size on the volitional swimming capacity of northern straight-mouth nase"	Scientific community	Paper
19.12.2022	Inspection of Equipment Following Recent Floods in the Duero River	General audience	Twitter
01.12.2022	Publication of the Paper: "An Open Surface Drifter for River Flow Field Characterization"	Scientific community	Paper
22.11.2022	Smart Fishways featured during Science Week	General audience	Twitter

10.10.2022	Smart Fishway presentation at The 2022 International Symposium on Ecohydraulics		Paper
12.09.2022	Smart Fishways project in the XIII course of fishway design	Scientific community	Twitter
01.09.2022	Publication of the Paper: "Brown Trout Upstream Passage Performance for a Fishway with Water Drops between Pools beyond Fish Passage Design Recommendations"	Scientific community	Paper
25.07.2022	Installation of sensor network and camera system in Portugal	Scientific community Industry-private companies	Twitter
13.07.2022	Field visit and presentation of Smart Fishways in Spain to Portuguese Students	Scientific community General audience	N/A
26.06.2022	Field Presentation of Smart Fishways to the Stakeholders of the LIFE Kantauribai Project	Scientific community Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	N/A
24.06.2022	Presentation of Field Installation Results at the SIBIC Conference	Scientific community Industry-private companies	Twitter Abstract Poster
23.06.2022	Iberian barbel fish movements through Guma hydropower plant at SIBIC	Public administration and policymakers	Twitter
23.06.2022	Effect of hydrological variability in V-flats presentation at SIBIC		Twitter
20.06.2022	Visit to field installations and GEA lab with RIBES Fellow	Scientific community	Twitter
08.03.2022	Presentation of Smart Fishways to the Stakeholders of the DivAqua LIFE Project	Scientific community Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers	N/A
26.01.2022	Smart Fishways presentation at Cfb, TalTech, Estonia	Scientific community	N/A
15.12.2021	Publication of the Paper: "Fish Upstream Passage Through Gauging Stations. Experiences With Iberian Barbel in Flat-V Weirs"	Scientific community	Paper
25.11.2021	Smart Fishways webpage release and Twitter account created	Scientific community Industry-private companies Public administration and policymakers General audience	Web Twitter
15.11.2021	Visit to field and presentation on Smart Fishways sensors to Master Students	General audience	N/A
13.11.2021	A step to Smart Fishways. The first paper of the project	Scientific community	Paper Twitter
10.11.2021	Smart Fishways in the week of the science	General audience	Twitter
01.10.2021	First water level sensor developed	General audience	Web
23.09.2021	"Official Presentation of Smart Fishways at UVa during the European Researchers' Night	General audience Scientific community	Youtube
15.09.2021	Smart Fishways logo release	General audience	N/A

Figure 4. Audience Distribution Pie Chart showcasing the proportional representation of the Scientific Community, Industry-Private Companies, Public Administration and Policymakers, and the General Audience.

Additional dissemination activities include my participation in official BSc and Master's degree courses at the University of Valladolid (UVA), covering a range of subjects such as electronics, sensors, automation, applied hydraulics, hydraulic infrastructure, control systems, and conservation hydrology. The insights and outcomes from the Smart Fishways project have been instrumental in clarifying specific topics within these courses.

Moreover, exploitation activities involve collaborations with the Itagra.ct team to discuss the potential commercialization of the developed technology. In these arrangements, while the University of Valladolid (Uva) maintains the intellectual property rights, Itagra.ct will take charge of exploiting the sensor technology.

For the most recent overview of activities, please visit the news section on our [webpage](#).